

ON THE ALKALOID OF *RAUWOLFIA CANESCENS*. PART V.

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Rauwolscine, the alkaloid of *Rauwolfia canescens* forms a methiodide on methylation with methyl iodide at room temperature. With alkali, the methiodide, $C_{21}H_{28}O_3N_2 \cdot CH_3I$, produces a betaine, $C_{21}H_{28}O_3N_2$, which has been named *isorauwolscine*. *Isorauwolscine* is free from methoxyl group and is an isomer of its parent alkaloid, rauwolscine. The betaine forms well defined salts. Its hydrochloride is colorless when freshly prepared but turns pink when exposed to air. Stepwise degradation of the betaine by exhaustive methylation leads to total fission producing isophthalic acid, harman and indole derivatives.

It was reported earlier (Mookerjee, this *Journal*, 1941, 18, 34, 485; 1943, 20, 11; 1946, 23, 6) that rauwolscine, the alkaloid of *Rauwolfia canescens* has the constitution (I)

as determined from the study of its several degradations, viz., pyrolysis, alkali fusion and zinc dust distillation etc. Since all these degradations had been performed under drastic conditions it was not possible to determine whether the hydroxyl and carbomethoxyl groups were in ring E in rauwolscine, and thus to find out their locations, stepwise degradations of the alkaloid under mild conditions, viz., by exhaustive methylation were thought reasonable. In connection with this investigation rauwolscine has been methylated with methyl iodide in acetone and the action of alkali on rauwolscine methiodide has been studied. Rauwolscine methiodide ($C_{22}H_{29}N_2O_3I$, m.p. 268° , decomp.) when boiled with 10% aqueous potassium hydroxide produces a colorless, hygroscopic betaine, which has been named *isorauwolscine*. From the aqueous solution the free betaine could not be isolated in the pure state on account of its high solubility in water and its insolubility in all the organic solvents. However, both of its organic and inorganic salts have been prepared and analysed. From the analyses of the salts of the betaine, the formula of *isorauwolscine* has been found to be $C_{21}H_{28}O_3N_2$ and thus proved to be an isomer of its parent alkaloid, rauwolscine. It has already been discussed in a previous communication (Mookerjee, *ibid.*, 1941, 18, 33) that rauwolscine is a mono-acidic tertiary base although it contains a -NH group in ring B. This -NH group being in the indole nucleus has a very feeble basic character as a result of which it does not add up mineral acids and methyl iodide to form salts. Hence, on methylation with CH_3I the

tertiary N atom in ring C adds up CH_3I and the rauwoscine methiodide, thus obtained, has the following structure (II)

The subsequent conversion of the methiodide into the corresponding betaine, *isorauwoscine* (III), by the action of alkali takes place according to the following scheme.

*iso*Rauwoscine forms stable salts with hydrochloric acid and the hydrochloride gives colour reactions similar to those of rauwoscine and rauwoscinic acid (Mookerjee, *loc. cit.*). The salts of *isorauwoscine* are acidic to litmus but less soluble in water. The hydrochloride of *isorauwoscine*, $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_3\text{N}_2 \cdot \text{HCl}$, (Fig. 1), when freshly crystallised is colorless

Fig. 1

but turns deep pink when exposed to air. *iso*Rauwoscine produces a colorless perchlorate, $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_3\text{N}_2 \cdot \text{HClO}_4$, m.p. $256-58^\circ$ (decomp.) and its picrate is well crystalline and orange-yellow, m.p. $261-63^\circ$ (decomp.). The chloroplatinate of the betaine is an amorphous, pale orange substance, $(\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_3\text{N}_2)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{PtCl}_6$, m.p. 254° (decomp.). The crude *isorauwoscine*, when treated with hydrochloric acid in methanol, forms *isorauwoscine* hydrochloride which is found to be free from methoxyl group. It has been found, however, strange that *isorauwoscine* is quite stable to 10-15% alkali like rauwoscine and when distilled with 25-30% potassium hydroxide it suffers total fission producing indole and its derivatives. Attempts were made to prepare *isorauwoscine* in pure

state from rauwoscine methiodide on treatment with silver oxide. Silver oxide reaction product is a gummy substance which on distillation decomposes at $300^\circ/5$ mm. producing harman (IV) and an identified indole derivative, thus, suffering no milder cleavage like the parent base, rauwoscine. *iso*Rauwoscine on distillation with potassium

hydroxide decomposes into simpler fragments from which a non-nitrogenous substance has been isolated and identified as *isophthalic acid* (V) and also a nitrogenous portion which is still an unidentified indole derivative. Thus, it has not been possible to gather further information regarding the position of hydroxyl and carbomethoxy groups in rauwolsine molecule from studies of *isorauwolsine* and its salts.

(IV)

(V)

EXPERIMENTAL

Rauwolsine Methiodide—A mixture of rauwolsine (5.0 g.) and MeI (5 g.) in dry acetone (100 c.c.) was allowed to stand for 2 days at room temperature, when colorless, shining, hexagonal flakes of rauwolsine methiodide separated, m.p. 268° (decomp.), yield 4.8 g. On recrystallisation from alcohol and water the m. p. did not change. The shining transparent crystals turn opaque when kept overnight and it has been found to contain one molecule of acetone of crystallisation. [Found (in a sample dried in *vacuo* over P₂O₅ for 36 hours): C, 53.38; H, 5.97; N, 5.64; I, 25.95. C₃₁H₂₈O₃N₂.CH₃I requires C, 53.22; H, 5.85; N, 5.64; I, 25.61 per cent].

isoRauwolsine Hydrochloride.—Rauwolsine methiodide (2.0 g.) was boiled with aqueous potassium hydroxide (10%, 20 c.c.) when it completely passed into solution. The latter on subsequent concentration to 5 c.c. precipitated colorless needles. These are highly soluble in water and insoluble in organic solvents and thus could not be isolated in the pure state. The needles were dissolved in the least amount of hydrochloric acid (2N, 50 c.c.). The solution was concentrated to 10 c.c. and allowed to stay overnight when stout leaflets of the hydrochloride were deposited, m.p. 261-63° (decomp.). The hydrochloride is sparingly soluble in alcohol. It possesses one molecule of water of crystallisation, which is completely removed on drying in *vacuo* over P₂O₅ for four hours at 115°. *isoRauwolsine hydrochloride* is acidic to litmus and liberates iodine from potassium iodide and potassium iodate. It is dextro-rotatory, $[\alpha]_D^{20} = +98.5$ (0.1269 g. substance in 50 c.c. water; $l = 50$ mm.). It is colorless when freshly prepared but slowly turns pink in air. [Found (in a specimen dried in *vacuo* over P₂O₅ for 4 hours at 115°): C, 64.78; H, 7.09; N, 7.28; Cl, 9.3. C₂₁H₂₈O₃N₂.HCl requires C, 64.54; H, 6.91; N, 7.17; Cl, 9.09 per cent].

The betaine hydrochloride gives the following colour reactions with concentrated sulphuric acid and other alkaloidal reagents.

TABLE I

Reagent.	Colour.
Conc. H_2SO_4 ...	An indigo-blue colour is developed first and then it is slowly discharged
Conc. $H_2SO_4 + K_2Cr_2O_7$...	A navy-blue colour which deepens on adding more $K_2Cr_2O_7$ and then quickly changes to purplish blue and finally to pale red.
Erdmann's reagent ...	A bluish green colour changing to olive-green and finally to yellow.
Mandelin's reagent ...	A green colour gradually changing to olive-green, yellowish green and yellow.

Perchlorate of isoRauwolfscine.—On adding an excess of perchloric acid (30%) to an aqueous solution of impure betaine, microscopic needles of betaine perchlorate separated. These on crystallisation from water melted at $256-58^\circ$ (decomp.). The perchlorate is soluble in water and acidic to litmus. [Found (in a sample dried *in vacuo* over P_2O_5 for 6 hours at $125^\circ-130^\circ$): N, 6.28; Cl, 8.11. $C_{21}H_{26}O_3N_2 \cdot HClO_4$ requires N, 6.16; Cl, 7.8 per cent].

Picrate of isorauwolfscine was obtained as orange-yellow shining plates by similar process and a saturated solution of picric acid in water was used. The picrate crystallised from alcohol in plates, m.p. $261-63^\circ$ (decomp.). [Found (in a sample dried *in vacuo*): N, 9.71. $C_{21}H_{26}O_3N_2 \cdot C_6H_2OH(NO_2)_3 \cdot 3 C_2H_5OH$ requires N, 9.71 per cent].

Chloroplatinate of isorauwolfscine was prepared by adding an excess of an aqueous solution of platinum chloride (5%) to a faintly acid solution of betaine hydrochloride. The amorphous, pale orange precipitate was washed several times with water acidulated with hydrochloric acid. The precipitate was dried at 100° over P_2O_5 for 6 hours *in vacuo*. The dried sample melted at 254° (decomp.). [Found (in a dry sample): Pt, 17.13. $(C_{21}H_{26}O_3N_2)_2 \cdot H_2PtCl_6$ requires Pt, 17.44 per cent].

Action of moist Silver Oxide on Rauwolfscine Methiodide.—Rauwolfscine methiodide (1.0 g.) in water (100 c.c.) was boiled for 15 minutes with freshly prepared moist silver oxide (1.5 g.). The mixture was filtered and the filtrate was evaporated under reduced pressure and the gummy residue separated was non-crystalline. On distillation at $300^\circ/5$ mm. the residue decomposed and yielded a dark brown distillate which was digested with ether. The latter on resolution with hydrochloric acid (90 c.c., 1%) produced two fractions: (A) basic and (B) non-basic.

Isolation of Harman from the Basic Fraction (A).—The hydrochloric acid digest contained the basic fraction. It was well cooled and basified with 1% sodium hydroxide. The base separated was taken up in ether on shaking (200 c.c.). The ether on drying and evaporation produced a semi-solid residue which crystallised from benzene in colorless needles, m.p. 231° . Twice recrystallisation from the same solvent gave pure harman which did not depress the m.p. when mixed with a sample of synthetic harman. [Found (in a dry sample): C, 79.28; H, 5.26; N, 15.30. Calc. for $C_{12}H_{10}N_2$: C, 79.12; H, 5.49; N, 15.38 per cent].

The ethereal solution was washed with water, dried and evaporated. The oily residue having a faecal smell, like skatole, gave positive pine chip test but all the methods to prepare its crystals and its crystalline picrate failed.

Distillation of isoRauwolscine at 290°-300° with KOH and Isolation of isoPhthalic Acid from the Degradation Product.—*isoRauwolscine* hydrochloride (5.0 g.) was distilled with potassium hydroxide from a metal-bath heated to 290°-300°. An oil having a faecal smell distilled over. The oil, however, did not form crystals and could not produce crystalline picrate, although positive test for pyrroles was obtained with pine chip. The non-volatile residue was dissolved in cold water (100 c.c.) and the dark red solution was filtered from insoluble resinous matters and freed from non-acidic oily impurities on extracting with ether. The aqueous alkaline solution on acidification (tested with Congo red) gave a brown mass which on sublimation at 310°-315° yielded a colorless solid, m. p. 346°. It crystallised from water as transparent glistening needles, m.p. 346°, yield 0.2 g. [Found (in a specimen dried in *vacuo* over P_2O_5 at 120° for 4 hours): C, 57.63; H, 3.80. $C_{12}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 57.84; H, 3.61 per cent]. The substance showed no depression in m.p. when mixed with synthetic *isophthalic* acid.

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Received July 6, 1930.